

Are you Ocean Literate?

A simple definition of Ocean Literacy is ‘an understanding of the ocean’s influence on you and your influence on the ocean’.

This could be appreciating how your rubbish might end up in the ocean and realising that half of the oxygen we breathe comes from the ocean!

There are 7 core principles to Ocean Literacy – did you know how amazing the ocean is?

1. Earth has one big ocean with many features

2. The ocean and life in the ocean shape the features of Earth

3. The ocean is a major influence on weather and climate

4. The ocean makes Earth habitable

5. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems

6. The ocean and humans are inextricably linked

7. The Ocean is largely unexplored

